

Portal Hypertensive Biliopathy Mimicking Cholangiocarcinoma: A Five-Case Report and Literature Review

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Abstract

Portal hypertensive biliopathy (PHB) represents a rare but significant complication of portal hypertension, particularly associated with portal cavernomas. This condition manifests with structural and functional abnormalities of the biliary tree due to extrahepatic vein obstruction. Often asymptomatic for extended periods, PHB eventually presents with intermittent jaundice and cholestasis. Diagnostic challenges abound, as PHB can mimic sclerosing cholangitis or cholangiocarcinoma. Here, we present the first documented series of PHB in Morocco, accompanied by a

More Information

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comprehensive review of the literature. Our report underscores the diagnostic complexities and highlights the need for heightened clinical suspicion and tailored management strategies in this rare pathology.

Introduction

Portal hypertensive biliopathy (PHB) refers to anatomical and functional abnormalities of the intrahepatic and extrahepatic bile ducts, occurring in the context of portal hypertension, primarily due to extrahepatic portal vein obstruction (EHPVO) or, less frequently, cirrhosis [1,2]. PHB can closely mimic autoimmune cholangitis, sclerosing cholangitis, and, most notably, cholangiocarcinoma, leading to diagnostic challenges [3].

Morphological changes in PHB include bile duct dilatation and stenosis, primarily caused by external compression from dilated venous plexuses attempting to decompress portal hypertension [4]. While initially

asymptomatic, PHB can progress to cholestasis, jaundice, biliary sludge, gallstones, cholangitis, or secondary biliary cirrhosis.

This paper presents the first documented series of five cases of PHB in Morocco, all initially misdiagnosed as cholangiocarcinoma, alongside a comprehensive literature review.

Case Report

Case 1:

A 66-year-old man with no prior history presented with intermittent cholestatic jaundice for eight years, recently worsening with pruritus and a 10 kg weight loss. Exam revealed jaundice, splenomegaly, and abdominal collaterals.

Figure 1: Significant Thickening of the Main bile duct with serpentine vascular structures on color Doppler

Laboratory investigations showed marked cholestasis with elevated total bilirubin at 306 mg/L (normal range: 3–10 mg/L), predominantly conjugated (direct bilirubin 186 mg/L (normal range: 1–3 mg/L); indirect bilirubin 120 mg/L (normal range: 2–9 mg/L)), elevated alkaline phosphatase at 255 IU/L (normal range: 45–132 IU/L), and thrombocytopenia with a platelet count of 77,000/mm³ (normal range: 150,000–400,000/mm³). An extensive etiological workup for other liver diseases, including viral and autoimmune serologies, procoagulant factors, IgG4 levels, and tumor markers, was negative.

Ultrasound demonstrated a hilar mass (3.4 × 3.1 cm) with bile duct dilatation, splenomegaly, and a portal cavernoma, initially suggesting cholangiocarcinoma. Doppler and CT revealed thickened bile ducts surrounded by serpiginous periportal collaterals

(Figure 1,2). MRCP confirmed cavernous transformation of the portal vein with venous collaterals compressing the common bile duct, producing significant biliary dilatation (Figure 3). Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed large esophageal varices, which were ligated, and a non-selective beta-blocker was initiated. Final diagnosis: PHB. The patient improved on ursodeoxycholic acid; shunt or transplantation was not feasible.

There is a proximal stricture of the main bile duct measuring 10.4 mm in length, with tapered ends on either side, within progressively enhancing pericholedochal structures after Gadolinium injection (D, E), indicating a vascular origin. These structures exhibit signal voids (corresponding to calcifications on the CT scan). An axial diffusion-weighted image

(G) (b value = 800 sec/mm²) indicates no diffusion restriction.

Figure 2: Abdominal CT scan in axial section without contrast injection (A), after contrast injection in the arterial phase (B) and portal phase (C)

Figure 3: Marked tortuous dilation of the proximal and distal intrahepatic bile ducts, giving a beaded appearance in some areas, can be seen in T2 (A, B) and T1 weighted imaging (C) and on MRCP (F)

Case 2

A 56-year-old man with cirrhosis and a history of smoking presented with right upper quadrant pain for one month, worsening in the last week. Exam revealed jaundice, splenomegaly, and abdominal collaterals. Labs showed cholestasis (bilirubin 14.1 mg/L, ALP 197 UI/L), Child-Pugh B8, and marked leukocytosis 31 460/mm³ (normal range: 4,000–10,000/mm³) with elevated CRP; viral and autoimmune serologies were negative. Doppler ultrasound demonstrated a portal cavernoma with periportal vascular structures (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Significant thickening of the main bile duct with serpentine vascular structures on color Doppler

Figure 5: Circumferential wall thickening involving the common bile duct extending to intra-hepatic bile ducts presenting an intermediate intensity in T2 (A) and T1-weighted imaging (B, C). There is also a progressive enhancement on post-contrast imaging in the arterial (D) and delayed phases (E)

MRCP showed bile duct wall thickening with serpiginous collaterals compressing the ducts,

intrahepatic dilatation, splenomegaly, and portosystemic collaterals — confirming PHB (Figure 5). The patient improved on ursodeoxycholic acid. Further workup for leukocytosis revealed a BCR-ABL mutation, establishing chronic myeloid leukemia. ERCP was considered but deferred. The patient was subsequently lost to follow-up.

Case 3

A 28-year-old woman with myelodysplastic syndrome and a heterozygous MTHFR mutation presented with three months of jaundice and 6 kg weight loss. Exam showed collateral circulation and massive splenomegaly (23 cm). Laboratory investigations showed marked hyperbilirubinemia with cholestasis and severe pancytopenia, including hypochromic anemia with hemoglobin at 5.1 g/dL (normal range: 12–16 g/dL), leukopenia at 1,310/mm³ (normal range: 4,000–10,000/mm³), and thrombocytopenia at 44,000/mm³ (normal range: 150,000–400,000/mm³). Investigations for other chronic liver diseases were negative.

MRCP demonstrated thickening of the main bile duct, periportal and perisplenic collaterals, and splenomegaly. Post-contrast sequences showed enhancement of the proximal hepatic canal wall with pericholedochal and pericholecystic collaterals — findings consistent with PHB (Figure 6). Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed grade II esophageal varices without red wale signs, and primary prophylaxis with carvedilol alone was initiated. The patient was treated with ursodeoxycholic acid, resulting in improvement of liver function tests.

Figure 6: An axial T2-FIESTA (A) an axial T1 (C) and a coronal T2-FIESTA demonstrate a wall thickening of the main biliary duct, multiple periportal, perisplenic venous collaterals and splenomegaly. An axial postcontrast T1-weighted arterial phase MR image (D) shows enhancement of the wall of the proximal hepatic canal along with pericholedochal and pericholecystic collaterals

Case 4

A 49-year-old man with asthma, past smoking, and occasional alcohol use was admitted for upper gastrointestinal bleeding (hematemesis and melena) associated with chronic pruritic jaundice. Exam revealed jaundice with excoriations, splenomegaly, abdominal collaterals, tense ascites, and melena.

Laboratory investigations showed anemia with hemoglobin at 11.5 g/dL (normal range: 13–17 g/dL), severe hyperbilirubinemia with marked cholestasis, and advanced liver dysfunction classified as Child–Pugh C10. Viral and autoimmune serologies were negative.

Ultrasound demonstrated a portal cavernoma with absent portal trunk. MRI confirmed cirrhotic liver with ascites, cavernous transformation, peribiliary vascular thickening causing severe CBD narrowing and intrahepatic dilatation, and superior mesenteric vein thrombosis. (Figures 7 and 8). Endoscopy revealed large esophageal varices, treated with band ligation, and hypertensive gastropathy.

Figure 7: MRCP, coronal T2-weighted image: Portal cavernoma with development of periportal and peribiliary collateral vessels, associated with dilatation of the intrahepatic bile ducts

The patient was treated with ursodeoxycholic acid, cholestyramine, and non-selective beta-blocker. Despite management, his clinical course rapidly worsened, and he died from a massive, fulminant gastrointestinal hemorrhage.

Figure 8: MRCP, axial T2-weighted image: Portal cavernoma with periportal collateral vessels causing biliary compression, consistent with portal hypertensive biliopathy

Case 5

A 58-year-old woman with prior pancreatic trauma surgery (2019) and cystogastrostomy (2022) for recurrent pseudocyst presented with two years of intermittent right upper quadrant pain and low-grade fever, without jaundice. Exam showed abdominal tenderness and collateral veins.

Labs revealed mild direct hyperbilirubinemia, anemia, and thrombocytopenia, with otherwise normal liver function; viral and autoimmune workup was negative. Ultrasound demonstrated a portal cavernoma with probable portal vein thrombosis and a multiloculated pancreatic head lesion with microcalcifications and ductal dilatation. The liver appeared normal, without biliary dilatation. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed large esophageal varices and portal hypertensive gastropathy; variceal band ligation was not performed.

A diagnosis of PHB was made. She was treated with ursodeoxycholic acid and carvedilol, with further management of the pancreatic lesion planned by endoscopic ultrasound.

Notably, HIV serology was systematically obtained in all patients to exclude HIV-related cholangitis and returned negative in all cases.

Discussion

Definition

Portal Hypertensive Biliopathy (PHB), also called Portal Cavernoma Cholangiopathy (PCC), refers to abnormalities of the intra- and extrahepatic bile ducts, cystic duct, and gallbladder in the setting of portal hypertension, most often due to extrahepatic portal vein obstruction (EHPVO) with cavernoma formation [5]. Typical changes include strictures, dilatations, stones, and choledochal varices [4].

Definitions have varied: Sarin et al. described PHB as biliary and gallbladder wall changes in portal hypertension [6], whereas Dhiman et al. proposed a broader definition involving the entire biliary tract [7]. According to the 2014 Indian National Association for Study of the Liver (INASL) consensus, diagnosis of PCC requires three criteria: portal cavernoma, cholangiographic abnormalities (MRCP or ERC), and

exclusion of other causes [1,7]. All patients in our case series fulfilled these diagnostic criteria.

Epidemiology

PHB occurs almost exclusively in patients with EHPVO and cavernoma, with a reported prevalence of 81–100% (8,9). While rare in Western countries, higher rates are reported in India, South Korea, and Turkey (8–10). Cases in South America are scarce [4,10], and none had been documented in Morocco before our series. PHB is more common in non-cirrhotic portal hypertension, which accounts for ~40% of portal hypertension in developing countries, though cases in cirrhosis have also been described [2,11]. Our series illustrates both cirrhotic and non-cirrhotic PHB, consistent with literature.

Pathophysiology

PHB mainly results from EHPVO, where recanalization leads to cavernous transformation compressing bile ducts externally [1]. Causes of EHPVO include hepatopathy, bilio-pancreatic tumors, liver transplantation, omphalitis, abdominal sepsis, myeloproliferative disease, and coagulation disorders [12,13].

The bile duct is drained by two venous plexuses: the epicholedochal plexus of Saint and the paracholedochal plexus of Petren, connected to gastric, pancreaticoduodenal, and portal veins [5,14]. In portal hypertension, these plexuses dilate, compressing bile ducts. An additional ischemic mechanism has been proposed, with impaired blood supply leading to scarring, rigid strictures, and secondary duct dilatation [15]. In our series, Cases 1, 2, and 5 illustrate the compressive mechanism, while Cases 3 and 4 likely had an ischemic component, reflected by ductal wall thickening and long strictures. Together, they highlight the frequent mixed pattern observed in advanced PHB.

Clinical Presentation

PHB evolves in phases: asymptomatic, symptomatic, and complicated. Cholangiographic changes are seen in 80–90% of patients with EHPVO, but most remain asymptomatic for years. Symptoms usually appear in the 3rd–4th decade, 8–14 years after portal hypertension onset [3].

Case 5 illustrates this phase, with portal cavernoma and only minimal symptoms for years.

The asymptomatic stage may show early cholangiographic changes (irregularity, serration, nodular impressions, strictures) with or without mild biochemical abnormalities [16]. Case 1 reflects this progression, with chronic intermittent jaundice evolving over eight years before diagnosis.

Symptomatic disease is marked by jaundice, cholestasis, biliary pain, or cholangitis, often due to stones. Cases 2 and 3 correspond to this stage, both presenting with jaundice and biochemical cholestasis associated with biliary abnormalities. Advanced stages

present with complex strictures (>2 cm, multifocal, intra- and extrahepatic) and biliopancreatic complications, where treatment is challenging [3,17]. Case 4 exemplifies this complicated stage, combining severe strictures, variceal bleeding, and liver failure.

Differential Diagnosis

PHB must be differentiated from a wide spectrum of biliary diseases, including primary/secondary sclerosing cholangitis, cholangiocarcinoma, ischemic cholangiopathy, autoimmune or chronic pancreatitis, primary biliary cholangitis, gallbladder disease, congenital malformations, and Budd–Chiari syndrome. In tropical regions, AIDS cholangiopathy and parasitic biliary disease should also be considered [18].

Most importantly, our series demonstrates that PHB can easily be misdiagnosed as cholangiocarcinoma. Such an error may expose patients to unnecessary cancer therapies or major surgery—interventions that are invasive, expensive, and often inaccessible in resource-limited contexts. This underscores the need for heightened awareness among radiologists and gastroenterologists.

Diagnostic Imaging

Imaging reveals both vascular and biliary abnormalities. Vascular findings include portal vein thrombosis or non-visualization, cavernoma formation, and portosystemic collaterals. Biliary features include ductal stenosis, upstream dilatation, irregular or wavy CBD contours, angulation, stones, and wall thickening. Importantly, enhancement patterns may mimic cholangiocarcinoma [3-5]. In our series, several patients were initially misdiagnosed with hilar cholangiocarcinoma on ultrasound or CT, whereas the definitive diagnosis of portal hypertensive biliopathy was established on MRCP, underscoring the diagnostic challenge for radiologists.

- **Ultrasound/Doppler:** first-line tool [1,4,7,10]. It shows cavernomatous transformation, periportal collaterals, CBD narrowing with dilatation, choledocholithiasis, and varices. Doppler helps differentiate collaterals from masses and detect cirrhosis or splenomegaly.
- **EUS:** improves detection of small stones and strictures, and with Doppler, identifies pericholedochal collaterals not visible on standard imaging—helpful in distinguishing PHB from PSC or cholangiocarcinoma [5,19].
- **CT:** demonstrates cavernoma, pericholedochal vessels, biliary wall thickening, stenosis/dilatation, and cirrhotic changes. Useful to exclude malignant obstruction or tumoral thrombosis, but limited for follow-up due to radiation [3,20].
- **MRCP:** modality of choice. It shows bile duct irregularities, strictures, choledocholithiasis, and collaterals, and helps distinguish benign smooth narrowing from malignant strictures. Classifications by

Llop and Chandra describe varicoid, fibrotic, and mixed types [2,3,21,22].

- **ERCP,** once the gold standard, is now mainly diagnostic when MRCP is inconclusive. Findings often overlap with cholangiocarcinoma or PSC, reinforcing the risk of misdiagnosis [23].

Management

Treatment of PHB is indicated only in symptomatic patients. Asymptomatic cases should be followed with Doppler ultrasound and MRCP, since early changes may progress over time [5,24]. In our series, Case 5 remained minimally symptomatic and was managed conservatively with UDCA and surveillance.

- **Medical therapy** with ursodeoxycholic acid (10–15 mg/kg/day) often improves cholestasis and symptoms [19,22]. Management of portal hypertension may include beta-blockers or variceal ligation, while obstructive jaundice can require biliary decompression. This approach was effective in Cases 1, 2, 3, and 5, who all showed biochemical improvement on UDCA.
- **Endoscopic therapy** is the first step in symptomatic disease with cholestasis or cholangitis. Sphincterotomy with stone extraction [25], balloon dilatation, or stenting of strictures [26] are the main options, although hemobilia remains a risk due to peribiliary collaterals [15,27]. These procedures are often used as a bridge to shunt surgery (25). In our experience, Case 4 could not undergo ERCP because of severe thrombocytopenia and coagulopathy, underlining the difficulty of endoscopic management in advanced PHB.

- **Portal decompression** through surgical shunts or TIPS is the cornerstone when feasible, reducing peribiliary collaterals and improving cholangiographic abnormalities [1]. However, limited access and high occlusion rates, especially in low-resource settings, restrict their use. Patients with extensive thrombosis, such as Case 4, are not candidates for shunting and must be managed conservatively or with endoscopic stenting [28,29].

Biliary diversion surgery (hepaticojejunostomy, choledochoduodenostomy, or Roux-en-Y reconstruction) may be considered when symptoms persist despite portal decompression, though bleeding risk is significant [30].

Liver transplantation is reserved for patients who progress to secondary biliary cirrhosis or end-stage liver disease.

Conclusion

Portal hypertensive biliopathy, most often due to extrahepatic portal vein obstruction, can closely mimic cholangiocarcinoma, making diagnosis challenging. In our series, several patients were initially misdiagnosed as having hilar cholangiocarcinoma before MRCP established the correct diagnosis.

Management depends on symptoms: UDCA may improve cholestasis, endoscopic therapy can relieve stones or strictures, and shunt surgery or TIPS remains the cornerstone when feasible. Advanced cases may require biliary diversion or transplantation.

Misdiagnosis may expose patients to unnecessary, invasive, and costly cancer treatments. Greater awareness among gastroenterologists, radiologists, and surgeons is crucial to ensure timely recognition and appropriate management of PHB.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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